

LIST OF CONFERENCE FOUND IN SMS 2012-2019.

Published studies	Conference name	Acronym	GGs Rating ^a	Conference Rank ^b	Conference proceedings
1	ACM International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining	SIGKDD	A++	A	✓
1	Usenix Security Symposium	USENIX-Security	A++	A	✓
1	Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences	HICSS	A+	A1	✓
1	International Semantic Web Conference	ISWC	A+	A1	✓
1	International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement	ESEM	A	A2	✓
1	International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering	ISESE	A-	B	✓
1	International Conference on Computational Science	ICCS	B	A2	✓
2	IEEE International Conference on eScience	eScience	B	B1	✓
1	International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management	EKAW	B	B1	✓
1	International Conference on Software Engineering and Knowledge Engineering	SEKE	B	B1	✓
1	IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing Technology and Science	CLOUDCOM	B	B2	✓
1	International Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work in Design	CSCWD	B-	B2	✓
1	International Provenance and Annotation Workshop	IPAW	B-	B2	✓
1	IEEE Conference on Computer Communications	IEEE INFOCOM	-	A	✓
2	International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems	ICEIS	-	B1	✓
1	IEEE International Conference Global Software Engineering	ICGSE	-	B2	✓
1	IEEE International Enterprise Distributed Object Computing Conference Workshops	EDOCW	-	B3	✓
2	IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine	BIBM	-	B4	✓
1	IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Data Acquisition and Advanced Computing Systems Technology and Applications	IDAACS	-	B4	✓
1	IEEE International Symposium on Applied Computational Intelligence and Informatics	SACI	-	B4	✓
1	Asia-Pacific Network Operations and Management Symposium	APNOMS	-	C	✓
1	International Conference on Data Integration in the Life Sciences	DILS	-	-	Book Series Q2
1	International Workshop on Advanced Computing and Analysis Techniques in Physics Research	ACAT	-	-	Journal Q3
1	International Conference on Information Technology and Systems	ICITS	-	-	Book Series Q3
1	International Conference on Sensor Networks	SENSORNE TS	-	-	✓
1	IEEE/ACM International Workshop on Software Engineering for Science	SE4Science	-	-	✓
1	International Design Engineering Technical Conferences and Computers and Information in Engineering Conference	IDETC/CIE	-	-	✓
1	Proceedings of SPIE - The International Society for Optical Engineering	SPIE	-	-	✓
1	International Conference on Information Society	i-Society	-	-	✓
1	International Conference Distributed Computing and Gridtechnologies in Science and Education	GRID	-	-	✓
1	Knowledge Management for Health Care Procedures	ECAI-K4HeIP	-	-	✓

^a GII-GRIN-SCIE (GGs) Conference Rating. <http://gii-grin-scie-rating.scie.es/>^b <http://www.conferenceranks.com>

LIST OF BOOKS FOUND IN SMS 2012-2019.

Published studies	Book name	Indexation
1	Guide to Advanced Empirical Software Engineering	Springer London ^a
1	Web Semantics for Textual and Visual Information Retrieval	Web of Science ^b

^a <https://www.springer.com>

^b <http://www.webofknowledge.com>